

On the order of magnetic transition in MnCo_{1-x}Fe_xGe (x = 0.20, 0.06 and 0.03) mechanical alloys

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Abstract

Mechanically amorphized MnCo_{1-x}Fe_xGe (x = 0.20, 0.06 and 0.03) were used as precursors to obtain hexagonal austenite single phase samples. Combining thermomagnetic and magnetocaloric analysis and in situ X-ray diffraction, we observed that the presence of a distribution of transition temperatures jeopardizes the first order character of the magnetoelastic transition from the ferromagnetic to paramagnetic state. Both magnetothermal and in situ X-ray diffraction identify the presence of such distribution and first order character of the magnetoelastic transition.

Keywords: mechanical alloying, order transition, magnetocaloric effect, magnetoelastic transition

1. Introduction

There is an important awareness in our society to reduce the energetic consumption. To achieve this goal is necessary to develop new technological applications, among which magnetic refrigeration based on the magnetocaloric effect (MCE) could be an excellent candidate for its high efficiency compared to conventional refrigeration systems [1]. In this sense, it is desirable to obtain materials that show large MCE around room temperature in the context of domestic applications. MCE consists in the heating or cooling of a magnetic material when a magnetic field is applied or removed [2]. To indirectly characterize this phenomenon, the magnetic entropy change, ΔS_M , can be used, which is related to the temperature change of magnetization, M , by the Maxwell relation.

$$\Delta S_M = \mu_0 \int_0^{H_{max}} \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial T} \right)_H dH \quad (1)$$

Where μ_0 is the permeability of vacuum, H is the magnetic field and T is the temperature. From this equation, it is deduced that the MCE is maximum around a phase transition (high variation in M). Transitions can be classified into two categories: first (FOPT) or second order (SOPT) character, attending to the order of the derivative of energy to be discontinuous. On the one hand, FOPT materials are characterized by a larger MCE response than those with SOPT but with significant values restricted to a smaller

temperature range and, generally, affected by hysteresis. On the other hand, although SOPT materials show smaller ΔS_M peaks than the FOPT materials, significant values extend to a wider temperature range and thermal hysteresis are absent and magnetic hysteresis can be negligible in soft magnetic materials.

In the present study we focus on martensitic alloys, which magnetic transitions are very interesting for their MCE [3–9] due to the coupling between structure and magnetism during the transition. In particular, this work deals with MnCoGe intermetallic compounds, where Fe partially substitutes for Co, and produced by low temperature annealing of precursor amorphous mechanical alloys. It is worth noticing that conventional production process of these alloys leads to samples with a on heating reversible transformation at about 420 K from a martensitic orthorhombic phase (TiNiSi type structure with a space group $Pnma$) to an austenitic hexagonal phase (Ni₂In-type structure with a space group $P6_3/mmc$)[10]. For MnCoGe, the Curie temperatures of hexagonal austenite and orthorhombic martensite are 276 K and 355 K, respectively [11]. As a result, the martensite transformation occurs in the paramagnetic state, which is not relevant to MCE. However, the magnetostructural martensitic transformation can be tuned to overlap with Curie temperature of both phases by applying physical pressure or chemical modifications [12–14], so that FOPT can be found around room temperature. In particular, partial substitution of Fe for Co can be a good compositional change to improve MCE [14]. However, the formation of the intermetallic phase of interest is not simple and thermal treatments at high temperatures for long times are needed [15–17], which can be overcome by using precursor systems produced by mechanical alloying [18]. Through this technique, micrometric powder particles are obtained, with crystallite size in the order of ~10 nanometers, or even with amorphous structure. The homogeneity of such precursors can reduce both the temperature and the annealing time needed to produce the intermetallic phase of interest from them [19].

In this work, the characteristics of the magnetic transition in MnCo_{1-x}Fe_xGe ($x = 0.20, 0.06$ and 0.03) series are analyzed taking into account the presence of a distribution of transition temperatures and in situ microstructural measurements. The field exponent of ΔS_M , n , and its dependency on the nature of the order transition as well as the existence of a distribution of transition temperatures were studied and related to the in-situ evolution of cell volume as a function of temperature.

2. Experimental

Production of the $\text{MnCo}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_x\text{Ge}$ (in at. %), with $x = 0.20, 0.06$ and 0.03 series follows the same steps as in [19,20]. First, a mixture of powders (purity >99 %) was milled in Ar atmosphere in a Fritsch Pulverisette Vario 4 planetary mill in order to produce homogeneous precursors (10 mm diameter steel balls; 80 cm³ hardened steel vials; ball to powder mass ratio 10:1; ratio between rotational speeds of vials and main disk –2). Second, samples were heated up to 723 K to develop the intermetallic phase.

Chemical composition was performed by X-ray fluorescence, XRF, (EAGLE III) and microstructure characterization by X-ray diffraction, XRD, (D8 Advance A25 diffractometer at room temperature and Bruker D8C diffractometer for controlled temperature and atmosphere experiments, Cu-K α radiation in both). X-ray analysis software used was version 4.1, Bruker DIFFRAC.EVA (phase identification) and version 6.0, Bruker DIFFRAC.TOPAS (Rietveld refinement). Thermal treatments were performed in a DSC7 Perkin-Elmer calorimeter operating in Ar flow at a heating rate of 20 K/min. A Lakeshore 7407 Vibrating Sample Magnetometer (VSM) was used to study field and temperature dependence of magnetization (maximum applied field 1.5 T). Magnetic entropy change was calculated from isothermal magnetization curves applying the Maxwell relation, described in Eq. 1, with the help of Magnetocaloric Effect Analysis program [21].

3. Results

3.1 Composition of powders

The chemical composition of 100 h milled sample with $x = 0.20$ can be found in [19]. For the other two samples, the general behavior is the same concerning Ge and transition metals content (ascribed to brittle character of Ge and ductile one of the transition metals). This leads to slight deviations with respect to the nominal composition, as shown in **Table 1**. However, in the following we will refer to the nominal composition for simplification.

Table 1. Composition observed by X-ray microfluorescence ($\text{MnCo}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_x\text{Ge}$)

x = 0.20			x = 0.06			x = 0.03		
Element	At. % expected	At. % observed	Element	At. % expected	At. % observed	Element	At. % expected	At. % observed
Mn	33.33	30.8 ± 0.2	Mn	33.33	32.9 ± 0.1	Mn	33.33	33.5 ± 0.2
Co	26.67	25.0 ± 0.2	Co	31.33	27.8 ± 0.2	Co	32.33	29.5 ± 0.2
Fe	6.67	7.0 ± 0.1	Fe	2.00	4.3 ± 0.4	Fe	1.00	2.4 ± 0.6
Ge	33.33	37.2 ± 0.3	Ge	33.33	35.0 ± 0.2	Ge	33.33	34.7 ± 0.5

$\text{Mn}_{0.92}\text{Co}_{0.75}\text{Fe}_{0.21}\text{Ge}_{1.12}$ $\text{Mn}_{0.99}\text{Co}_{0.83}\text{Fe}_{0.13}\text{Ge}_{1.05}$ $\text{Mn}_{1.00}\text{Co}_{0.88}\text{Fe}_{0.07}\text{Ge}_{1.04}$

3.2 Microstructure and thermal stability

Fig. 1 shows the room temperature XRD patterns of as-milled samples after two milling times. A more complete evolution with milling time, for the sample with $x=0.20$, can be found in [19,20]. In all the cases, an amorphous halo is formed as milling progresses beyond 30 h. After 50 h milling, a recrystallization process is detected which leads to the formation of the intermetallic phase of interest in this study ($P6_3/mmc$ space group). This recrystallization process is more evident in those samples with higher Fe content, specifically for $x = 0.20$ and 0.06 .

Fig. 2 shows DSC scans at 20 K/min from room temperature to 973 K for samples milled for 50 h. In all samples, exothermic transformation processes are observed ascribed to the crystallization of the amorphous phase developed during milling. **Table 2** shows parameters from DSC scans, such as peak temperatures and heat of transformation. XRD patterns of milled samples heated to 723 K at 20 K/min in the calorimeter (**Fig. 3**) show that, independently of Fe content, the stable phase formed is austenite intermetallic MnCoGe-type hexagonal phase as the single-phase present ($P6_3/mmc$ space group). There are some difference in relation to crystal size, the sample with highest Fe content shows $D = 14.1 \pm 0.3$ nm, however, samples with less Fe content, $x = 0.06$ and 0.03 , show similar crystal size, $D = 17.2 \pm 0.2$ and 17.1 ± 0.2 nm, respectively.

Table 2. Parameters from DSC scans

Fe content	x = 0.20	x = 0.06			x = 0.03	
Peak temperature (K)	562	576	634	873	576	634
Transformation heat (J/g)	52 ± 1	63 ± 1			66 ± 1	

Fig. 1. Room temperature XRD patterns of mechanically alloyed $\text{MnCo}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_x\text{Ge}$ ($x = 0.20, 0.06$ and 0.03) after 30 and 50 h milling.

Fig. 2. DSC scans at 20 K/min from room temperature to 973 K for samples milled for 50h $\text{MnCo}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_x\text{Ge}$, where $x = 0.20$ (black), $x = 0.06$ (blue) and $x = 0.03$ (red). The arrow indicates the magnitude and nature of the transformations; in this case, all of them are exothermic transformations.

Fig. 3. Room temperature XRD patterns of samples $\text{MnCo}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_x\text{Ge}$ milled for 50 h and heated up to 723 K at 20 K/min in the calorimeter. The corresponding differences between the experimental data and the Rietveld fittings are shown below each experimental pattern. The experimental data are shown in black, and the Rietveld fittings are shown in red. **D** indicates the crystal size and χ^2 indicates the goodness of fit.

3.3 Magnetic measurements

Fig. 4 (a) shows, as a function of Fe content, the isothermal magnetization curves for samples milled 50 h and heated up to 723 K at 20 K/min. Magnetization decreases as temperature approaches that of the magnetic transition from the ferromagnetic to the paramagnetic state.

Fig. 5 shows the magnetic entropy change for a maximum field change $\mu_0\Delta H = 1.5$ T as a function of Fe content and **Table 3** collects the main MCE parameters including refrigerant capacity defined as $RC_{FWHM} = \Delta S_M^{peak} \cdot \Delta T$ where ΔT is the full width at half maximum of MCE peak. As Fe content decreases, $|\Delta S_M|$ slightly increases. However, there is no monotonous trend in T_c and sample with $x = 0.06$ shows a slightly higher Curie temperature than the other two samples.

Fig. 4. Isothermal magnetization curves (**left**) and Arrot plots (**right**) for samples milled 50 h and heated up to 723 K at 20 K/min as a function of Fe content.

Table 3. MCE response at $\mu_0\Delta H = 1.5$ T as a function of Fe content

Fe content	Max $\Delta S_M \pm 0.01$ ($J \cdot kg^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$)	$RC_{FWHM} \pm 3$ ($J \cdot kg^{-1}$)	$T_C \pm 3$ (K)
0.20	-1.01	-66	272
0.06	-1.02	-62	279
0.03	-1.05	-61	275

Fig. 5. Temperature dependence of ΔS_M for samples milled for 50 h and heated up to 723 K at 20 K/min in the calorimeter as a function of Fe content. Black squares correspond to samples with $x = 0.20$, blue circles correspond to samples with $x = 0.06$, and red triangles correspond to samples with $x = 0.03$.

4. Discussion

The nature of the observed magnetic transition can be studied using the Banerjee criterion [22] which indicates that the slopes of the isotherms in the Arrot plots (H/M versus M^2) must be negative in the case of a first-order transition, whereas positive slopes are indicative of a second-order character of the transition.

Fig. 4 (b) shows the Arrot plots corresponding to the data shown in **Fig. 4** (a). Therefore, according to Banerjee criterion, these samples should exhibit a second order phase transition. However, recent results showed that there are other criteria that allow evaluating the order of the phase transition based on the field exponent of magnetic entropy change [23], which can identify more precisely the order of the transition.

The field dependence of the magnetic entropy change is represented as a power law of the field $\Delta S_M \propto H^n$ with an exponent n that, in general, is field and temperature dependent [24]. In the paramagnetic range, magnetization behaves according to the Curie-Weiss law, which leads to $n = 2$. In the ferromagnetic range and well below the transition, $n = 1$. Finally, at the transition temperature, T_c , for second-order phase transformations, the exponent n is related to the critical exponents of the material:

$$n(T_c) = 1 + \frac{1}{\delta} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta}\right) \quad (2)$$

Where β and δ are critical exponents and can be related to a third critical exponent, γ : $\delta = 1 + \gamma/\beta$.

Non-negligible effects of the demagnetizing factor, N [25] makes necessary to correct the magnetization curves from the demagnetizing field using the internal field, $H = H_{ap} - NM$, instead of the applied field H_{ap} . This was done with the aim to compare our results to the predictions of theoretical analyses that show that the field exponent n of magnetic entropy change presents a maximum of $n > 2$ only for first-order thermomagnetic phase transitions [23].

Fig. 6 shows the experimentally determined exponent n as a function of temperature for the different compositions for a maximum magnetic field change of 1 T for uncorrected (using H_{ap} , as solid symbols) and corrected (using $H = H_{ap} - NM$, as hollow symbols) curves of $M(T, H)$ assuming $N \sim 0.25$ (estimated from the deviation of exponent n for $T \ll T_C$ [26]). .

Fig. 6. Experimental $n(T)$ curves of samples milled for 50 h and heated up to 723 K at 20 K/min in the calorimeter as a function of Fe content for 1.0 T of applied field (uncorrected curves, solids symbols) or internal field (corrected curves using $N = 0.25$, hollow symbols).

Once considering the demagnetizing factor, the values of n at $T \ll T_C$ recover the expected value close to one. However, at T_C , values are clearly higher than the expected ones: $n^{peak} = 0.80, 0.81$ and 0.81 for $x = 0.20, 0.06$ and 0.03 , respectively, instead of $n^{peak} \sim 0.67$ for a mean field SOPT [24]. This fact can be due to the existence of inhomogeneities which can lead to the existence of a broad T_C distribution in these samples. Comparison between mean field value for pure phase, $n^{peak} \sim 0.67$, and obtained ones should lead to values of the width of the distribution around 10 K [27]. The source of this distribution could be compositional as it is known that T_C can be tailored in these compositions by changing the Fe content [10,28].

Fig. 7. (a) Experimental data for M_s , (b) dM_s/dT and (c) χ_p curves from the analysis of approach to saturation from $\Delta S_M(T)$ curves for samples $MnCo_{1-x}Fe_xGe$ with different Fe content (indicated in the legend), milled for 50 h and heated up 723 K at 20 K/min in the calorimeter. (d) Experimental peak temperatures for: dM_s/dT , χ_p and $\Delta S_M(T)$ curves (upper panel); (e) mean Curie temperatures, $\langle T_C \rangle$ (middle panel); and (f) standard deviation, ΔT_C , of the distribution of transition temperatures (lower panel) from Equations (3), (4) and (5), as a function of iron content.

Recently, Manchón-Gordón et al. proposed a method to obtain the parameters of a gaussian distribution of T_C (average value $\langle T_C \rangle$ and standard deviation ΔT_C), based on the Weiss model [29,30]. This method uses the dependence on $\langle T_C \rangle$ and ΔT_C of the inflexion point temperature, T_{inf} , of the saturation magnetization at zero field, $M_s(T)$, and the peak temperature, T_χ , of the paramagnetic susceptibility (χ_p), which can be obtained from the linear fitting of the law of approach to saturation of the $M(T, H)$ curves. This law can be simplified to: $M = M_S + \chi_p H$ where H is the internal field (magnetic fields above 1 T are

taken, so the effects of demagnetizing factor are negligible). Effects involved by structural inhomogeneities caused by defects within magnetic substances and effective anisotropy have not been considered. Additionally, the peak temperature of the MCE, T_{MCE} , also depends on $\langle T_C \rangle$ and ΔT_c . The following equations [31] describe such dependences:

$$T_{inf}^{Weiss} - \langle T_C \rangle = -0.732(6)\Delta T_c \quad (3)$$

$$T_{MCE}^{Weiss} - \langle T_C \rangle = -0.658(8)\Delta T_c \quad (4)$$

$$T_{\chi}^{Weiss} - \langle T_C \rangle = 0.503(24)\Delta T_c - 0.0040(7)\Delta T_c^2 \quad (5)$$

Where superscript Weiss indicates the use of this model to describe the magnetization.

Fig. 7 a, b and c show experimental data for the different studied compositions of M_S , dM_S/dT and χ_P from the analysis of approach to saturation (using a density of 6707 kg/m³). It can be seen how magnetization does not go to zero in the paramagnetic range. This may be due to the presence of ferromagnetic inhomogeneities. This remaining value of magnetization should correspond to 1% volume of magnetic impurities (using magnetic moment of iron).

Fig. 7 d shows the different experimental peak temperatures used in equations (3)-(5). Results are shown in **Fig. 7 e and f** for $\langle T_C \rangle$ and ΔT_c , respectively. Despite the large error, the estimated broadenings are 5, 12 and 10 K for $x = 0.03, 0.06$ and 0.2 , respectively. These values are in agreement with the expected increase in the n exponent due to the presence of a distribution [27]. The out of equilibrium method of sample production leading to this distribution can also explain that austenite phase stabilizes in our samples unlike results reported from other authors for similar compositions produced by arc-melting, where martensite phase is found [12]. In our study, mechanical alloying stabilizes the phase with higher entropy. **Fig. 8** shows the magnetic transition temperature obtained in our study along with the results from Li et al. [12].

Fig. 8. Magnetic transformation temperature as a function of Fe content. Hollow symbols correspond to martensite phase and full symbols to austenite phase. Squares are taken from [12] and circles are measurements from this work (average values from Weiss distribution are represented and error bars correspond to the standard deviation of the distribution).

Fig. 9 shows in situ XRD patterns of the different studied samples as a function of temperature (between 200 and 320 K). All samples show the austenite intermetallic as a single phase in all the studied range.

Fig. 9. XRD patterns as a function of temperature (between 200 and 320 K) of samples $\text{MnCo}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_x\text{Ge}$ milled for 50 h and heated up to 723 K at 20 K/min in the calorimeter. Circles correspond to hexagonal phase (austenite) and squares correspond to sample holder.

XRD results were analyzed by Rietveld fitting (goodness of fit below 1.3). **Fig. 10** shows the temperature evolution of lattice parameters, a and c , of the intermetallic phase. For $x = 0.06$, both lattice parameters linearly increase with temperature as a result of regular

thermal expansion. However, for the other two compositions, the lattice parameters do not present that simple behavior, but they can even decrease with temperature. This fact supports the characteristic corresponding to FOPT inferred from the behavior of the field exponent n but contradictory to the Arrott-plot. Certainly, there is a considerable volume variation without modification of the crystal structure (i.e. a magnetoelastic transition) as shown in **Fig. 11**. However, the presence of a distribution of Curie temperatures in the samples may jeopardize the weak FOPT character, in fact second order behavior prevails over first order contributions in Arrott-plots when the response of a mixture of phases is analyzed [32–35].

Fig. 10. Evolution as a function of temperature of lattice parameters, a and c , of the intermetallic phase detected by XRD.

Fig. 11. Evolution of cell volume of the intermetallic phase detected by XRD as a function of temperature. Red line indicates volume fitting for sample with $x = 0.20$.

It is observed that cell volume variation is more considerable for the sample with $x = 0.20$ and in the following we will refer to this sample. A curve fitting is proposed based on the assumption that the volumetric expansion coefficient, β , is the same for the ferromagnetic and paramagnetic phases. It is also important to consider the existence of a Curie

temperature distribution, in this way the volume of the sample as a function of temperature can be described as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 V &= V_0 \cdot (1 + \beta T) \cdot \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{T - \langle T_c \rangle}{\sqrt{2}\Delta T_c}\right) + V'_0 \cdot (1 + \beta T) \cdot \left(1 - \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{T - \langle T_c \rangle}{\sqrt{2}\Delta T_c}\right)\right) \\
 &= (1 + \beta T) \cdot \left[V_0 \cdot \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{T - \langle T_c \rangle}{\sqrt{2}\Delta T_c}\right) + V'_0 \cdot \left(1 - \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{T - \langle T_c \rangle}{\sqrt{2}\Delta T_c}\right)\right) \right]
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Where V_0 and V'_0 are the volumes of the ferromagnetic and paramagnetic phase at 0 K, respectively, and $\operatorname{erf}(x)$ is the error function, which can be defined as follows:

$$\operatorname{erf}(x) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^x e^{-u^2} du \tag{7}$$

The evolution of cell volume of the sample with $x = 0.20$ is shown as a function of the temperature with its respective fitting in **Fig. 11**. **Table 4** shows volume fitting parameters.

Table 4. Volume fitting parameters

V_0	$75.2 \pm 0.4 \text{ \AA}^3$
V'_0	$74.9 \pm 0.5 \text{ \AA}^3$
β	$(4.9 \pm 2.1) \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-1}$
$\langle T_c \rangle$	$265.5 \pm 1.2 \text{ K}$
ΔT_c	$23 \pm 5 \text{ K}$

It can be seen how $\langle T_c \rangle$ and ΔT_c are clearly different from those obtained by the previously applied distribution model. This latter value of $\langle T_c \rangle$ is closer to the inflection point of saturation magnetization. The reasons for these differences could be ascribed to the use of simple Gaussian distributions. Moreover, it is necessary to remember that equations (3)-(5) are based on mean field approximation whereas there are first-order contributions in this sample.

5. Conclusions

Mechanical alloying allows us to produce precursor amorphous Mn(Co,Fe)Ge alloys which, after annealing, develop hexagonal austenite phase. Despite, martensitic transformation to lower entropy orthorhombic phase is not detected, magnetic transition of higher entropy hexagonal phase shows interesting magnetocaloric properties.

However, the character of the transition is not straightforward. On the one hand, according to Banerjee's criterion, the transition should be second-order. However, this interpretation must be affected by the presence of a distribution of transition temperatures. On the other hand, analysis of the field dependence of ΔS_m states that the transition should be first-order, which is verified by detecting a cell volume variation, and thus a magnetoelastic transition, clearer for the sample with the highest Fe content.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

A. Vidal-Crespo: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - original draft. **J.J. Ipus:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Resources, Writing - review & editing. **J.S. Blázquez:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Resources, Writing - review & editing, Supervision. **C. F. Conde:** Methodology, Resources, Writing - review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interest or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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